

SPORTSHEALTH AND DEPENDENCE

BOVINE ELBOW JOINT

This is a mid-sagittal section of the knee joint. It is a complex joint, involving the femur, tibia, and patella, which is subdivided into a femorotibial and a patellofemoral joint. The compact and spongy or trabecular bone of the femur and tibia is very well depicted. The bone marrow is distributed among the trabecular bone. Between the femur and the tibia are the cruciate ligaments (anterior and posterior). Together with the menisci (not present in the image) are essential for keeping the stability of the joint. In the joint between the femur and patella, the articular cartilage can be observed.

11. Humerus. 2. Radius. 3. Ulna. 4. Calcaneal tuberosity. 5. Lateral collateral ligament. 6. Medial collateral ligament.

TRANSPARENT SECTION OF THE KNEE JOINT

This is a mid-sagittal section of the knee joint. It is a complex joint, involving the femur, tibia, and patella, which is subdivided into a femorotibial and a patellofemoral joint. The compact and spongy or trabecular bone of the femur and tibia is very well depicted. The bone marrow is distributed among the trabecular bone. Between the femur and the tibia are the cruciate ligaments (anterior and posterior). Together with the menisci (not present in the image) are essential for keeping the stability of the joint. In the joint between the femur and patella, the articular cartilage can be observed.

1. Femur. 2. Tibia. 3. Patella. 4. Patellar ligament. 5. Caudal (posterior) cruciate ligament. 6. Cranial (anterior) cruciate ligament.

OVINE LEG MUSCLES

This specimen shows a dissection of the muscles located in the leg of a sheep. Muscles extend from the knee region to the digits, therefore producing flexor and extension movements of the knee joint, as well as the tarsal and digital joints. Flexor muscles of the tarsus are positioned in the anterior (cranial) part of the specimen, whereas their opponent extensor tarsal muscles are in the posterior (caudal) part. The common calcaneal tendon (Achilles tendon) is a relevant landmark of this specimen. Muscles are attached proximally to the femur and tibia, mainly. Distally the leg muscles have long and strong tendons which terminate in the tarsal, metatarsal or phalangeal bones.

1. Femur 2. Patellar ligament. 3. M. quadriceps femoris. 4. Lateral collateral Ligament. 5. Extensor tarsal muscles. 6. M. Flexor ditialis lateralis (Flexor tarsal muscle). 7. M. gastrocnemius. 8. Common calcaneal tendon (Achilles tendon). 9. Digital extensor tendons. 10. Digital flexor tendons. 11. Common peroneal nerve. 12. Plantar ramus of tibial nerve

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